

NAIRR 2026 Annual Meeting Proceedings

<https://zenodo.org/communities/nairr2026>

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Plenaries and Keynotes

“Welcome Statements” (Plenary)

Wed, Mar 11, 9:00 AM - 10:00 AM, Regency ABCD Dana Brunson, Internet2

“State of the NAIRR” (Plenary)

Wed, Mar 11, 10:00 AM - 10:30 AM, Regency ABCD Katerina Antypas, National Science Foundation <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193254>

“Large-language models to decode RNA biology and empower RNA therapeutics” (Keynote)

Wed, Mar 11, 11:00 AM - 11:50 AM, Regency ABCD Gene Yeo, University of California San Diego <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193262>

“Olmo 3: Defining the Future of Open-Science AI with Model Flows” (Keynote)

Thu, Mar 12, 8:40 AM - 9:30 AM, Regency ABCD Hanna Hajishirzi, University of Southern Oregon <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193258>

“NAIRR for AI Education: Capacity-Building and Workforce Development (panel)” (Panel)

Thu, Mar 12, 9:30 AM - 10:30 AM, Regency ABCD Bernadette Boscoe, University of Southern Oregon; Karen Colbert, Keweenaw Bay Ojibwa Community College; Edgar Lobaton, North Carolina State University; Melanie Williamson, Bluegrass Community and Technical College *Moderated by: Tracy Camp, Computing Research Association*

“NAIRR Deep Partnerships (panel)” (Panel)

Thu, Mar 12, 11:00 AM - 12:00 PM, Regency ABCD Prasanna V Balachandran, University of Virginia; Peter Santhanam, The AI Alliance; Agung Julius, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute; Tom Gibbs, NVIDIA; Rohit Lal, University of Alabama in Huntsville; Sujit Roy, University of Alabama in Huntsville *Moderated by: Lacey Strahm, OpenMined*

“How Far We’ve Come: Research and Education Engagement with NAIRR Pilot Resources and Services” (Plenary)

Thu, Mar 12, 1:15 PM - 2:00 PM, Regency ABCD David Hart, Internet2; Shelley Knuth, University of Colorado Boulder <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193199>

“Future of AI Algorithms and Applications (panel)” (Panel)

Fri, Mar 13, 8:40 AM - 10:00 AM, Regency ABCD Jianyang Gu, Ohio State University; Adarsh Krishnamurthy, Iowa State University; Sarina Zhang, Texas A&M University; Amitava Majumdar, San Diego Supercomputing Center *Moderated by: Joe Stubbs, Texas Advanced Computing Center*

“NAIRR - Looking Forward, Conference Conclusion” (Plenary)

Fri, Mar 13, 11:35 AM - 12:00 PM, Regency ABCD Alejandro Suarez, National Science Foundation; Katerina Antypas, National Science Foundation

Lightning Talk Presentations

Wednesday, March 11, 1:15 PM – 3:30 PM

Foundation Model Development, Regency ABCD

1. “Towards Small, Open-Source, Multi-Modal Language Model Agents for Science and Society”

Xuan Wang, Virginia Tech <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19224053>

2. “BLISS: A Lightweight Bilevel Influence Scoring Method for Data Selection in Language Model Pretraining”

Mingrui Liu, George Mason University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193363>

3. “MergeBench: A Benchmark for Merging Domain-Specialized LLMs”

Han Zhao, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193369>

4. “Soma: Foundation Model for Multi-Modal Lunar Science using LRO Datasets”

Rohit Lal, University of Alabama in Huntsville <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193371>

5. “Synergistic Visual Intelligence for Multimodal Conversational AI”

Shengcao Cao, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193365>

6. “Intention-Adaptive LLM Fine-Tuning for Understanding and Generating Text Revisions”

Diane Litman, University of Pittsburgh <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193384>

- 7. “Learning from Synthetic Data Improves Multi-hop Reasoning”**
Katie Luo, Cornell University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193380>
- 8. “Reward-Guided Memetic Search for Inference-Time Optimization of LLM Responses”**
Son The Nguyen, University of Illinois Chicago
- 9. “Towards Scalable and Autonomous Humanoid Whole-Body Loco-Manipulation”**
Sirui Xu, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign

Computing & Data Infrastructure, and Platforms, Washington A

- 1. “Distributed Interpretability and Control for Large Language Models”**
Zining Zhu, Assistant Professor <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193325>
- 2. “Utilizing NAIRR Pilot Resources for Building Sustainable Blue Economy”**
Zhe Zhang, Texas A&M University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193323>
- 3. “MAPLE: A Multi-agent System for Portable Deep Learning across NAIRR Pilot Clusters”**
Zhao Zhang, Rutgers University
- 4. “Human perspectives on building and using an Intelligent Data Exploring Assistant (IDEA)”**
Matthew Widlansky, University of Hawaii at Manoa
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193319>
- 5. “Efficient Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback with Serverless Computing”**
Rui Wei, Stevens Institute of Technology; Dr. Hao Wang
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193481>
- 6. “Integrating AI Tools into Science Gateways Using NAIRR Resources”**
Maytal Dahan, Texas Advanced Computing Center
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193306>
- 7. “Anvil Notebook Service - An AI-enabled interactive platform for NAIRR researchers and educators”**
Erik Gough, Purdue University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193329>
- 8. “Advancing the NAIRR Pilot Portal: Sandboxes and Use Cases for Accessible AI Research”**
Sandra Gesing, San Diego Supercomputer Center
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193311>
- 9. “MLHub - An open source platform for developing and deploying AI Systems to NAIRR”**
Nathan Freeman, Texas Advanced Computing Center
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193327>
- 10. “Reevaluating Power Requirements for LLM Inference With Token Reuse”**
William Meng, University of Pennsylvania <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19473076>

Engineering, Safety, & Trustworthy AI, Washington B

1. "Leveraging NAIRR Pilot Resources for Advancing AI Face Analysis, Student Research, and Broader Engagement"
Shu Hu, Purdue University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193340>
2. "Extracting Formal Models From 5G Specifications For Security Analysis"
Imtiaz Karim, University of Texas at Dallas <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193361>
3. "Integrating Agentic AI and Digital Twins for Advanced Energy Systems: a Demo on a Cyber-Physical Testbed"
Yang Liu, Texas A&M University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193355>
4. "Rethinking Individual Fairness in Deepfake Detection"
Justin Li, Carmel High School <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193353>
5. "Promoting Trustworthy Use of Foundation Models via GAICO (Generative AI COmparator)"
Biplav Srivastava, University of South Carolina
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193351>
6. "AI-Enabled, Blockchain-Coordinated Microgrid Energy Trading for Scalable, Privacy-Preserving, and Resilient Operation"
Temitope Ajibola, Morgan State University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193331>
7. "Certifying GenAI Systems for Trustworthiness"
Isha Chaudhary, Univ of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193359>
8. "Consensus-Aware AV Behavior: Empirical Pareto-Guided Reinforcement Learning for Mixed Traffic"
Mohammad Elayan, University of Nebraska-Lincoln
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193335>
9. "Bootstrapping Embodied Reasoning"
Milan Ganai, Stanford University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193337>
10. "Implicit Neural Representations as a Geometric Abstraction for PDE Solvers"
Samundra Karki, Iowa State University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193345>

Physical & Earth Sciences, Potomac I/III

1. "MATEY for long-horizon prediction of plasma edge dynamics"
Hunor Csala, Oak Ridge National Laboratory <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193401>
2. "Creating Mobile Education AI Tutors: Socratic and Embodied"
Mina Johnson-Glenberg, Arizona State University; Feni Chaudhari
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193391>

- 3.** “Iterative learning for out-of-distribution data in multiscale modeling of history-dependent materials”
Yupeng Zhang, UCLA <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193428>
- 4.** “Evaluating Vision–Language Models for Agricultural Image Understanding and Metadata Enrichment”
Ana Lucic, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19224055>
- 5.** “LLM-Driven Security Analysis for Cellular Networks: Vulnerability Discovery Agent and Benchmarking”
Tian Xie, Utah State University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193422>
- 6.** “MAE-pretrained Arctic ViT: A Regional-scale, Domain-Adapted Remote-Sensing foundation model”
Amal Perera, University of Connecticut (Storrs, CT)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193414>
- 7.** “Development of AI Weather Models for the Prediction of Atmospheric Rivers and Extreme Precipitation”
Agniv Sengupta, University of California San Diego
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193418>
- 8.** “Segmenting Radio Frequency Interference”
Preshanth Jagannathan, National Radio Astronomy Observatory
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193386>
- 9.** “SPIn4D: Spectropolarimetric Inversion in Four Dimensions with Deep Learning”
Yannik Glaser, University of Hawaii at Manoa <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193405>
- 10.** “Fast Rotation Measure Synthesis using Simulation-Based Inference”
Arpan Pal, National Radio Astronomy Observatory
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193397>

Biomedical, Health, & Life Sciences, Potomac II/IV

- 1.** “MolSnap: Efficient Causality-Aware Multimodal Molecular Generation via Variational Mean Flow”
Qiang Cheng, University of Kentucky <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193267>
- 2.** “Towards an End to”Uncertain Significance”: Translating the Genome into Clinical Decisions via Generative AI”
Avi Sahu, University of New Mexico Cancer Center
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193301>
- 3.** “MicroTraitLLM: A RAG-based, Microbe-focused LLM for Researchers”
Glen Rogers, Drexel University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193287>
- 4.** “BioCLIP 2: Emergent Properties from Scaling Hierarchical Contrastive Learning”
Jianyang Gu, The Ohio State University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193275>

- 5.** “Towards a universal model of tissue cellular architecture”
Kai Tan, Children’s Hospital of Philadelphia <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193291>
- 6.** “Establishing a Convex Cost-Accuracy Efficiency Frontier for Genomic Inference via Unsupervised Adaptive Routing”
Sitao Huang, Princeton University
- 7.** “Accelerating Causal Network Discovery of Alzheimer’s Disease Biomarkers via Scientific Literature-based Retrieval Augmented Generation”
Xiaofan Zhou, University of Illinois Chicago <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193293>
- 8.** “Privacy-Preserving Genomics Data Sharing on the NAIRR”
Sikha Pentyala, University of Washington Tacoma
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193297>
- 9.** “Unified Self-Supervised Vision Pretraining for Multi-Task Biodiversity Applications”
Shivani Chiranjeevi, Iowa State University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193283>
- 10.** “Optimizing private clinical text generation across data silos”
John Gounley, Oak Ridge National Laboratory <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193269>

Social Sciences, Education, & Workforce Development, Conference Theater

- 1.** “Scaling Tonally-Sensitive African Language Models with NAIRR Resources”
Michael Odokara-Okigbo, ESM Global Productions
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193454>
- 2.** “Empowering Ambition: The Impact of Compute Access on Student Project Scope in NLP Courses”
Nic Herndon, East Carolina University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193452>
- 3.** “Hands-on Ethical Inquiry: A Participatory and Exploratory Lab Model for AI/ML Ethics Education”
Changjia Yang, University Of Maryland, Baltimore County
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193449>
- 4.** “AI-enabled process-level cognitive assessment in Minecraft: Background”
Dennis Barbour, Washington University in St. Louis
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193447>
- 5.** “An AI infrastructure to advance research in reducing poverty and informing social policy”
Neeti Pokhriyal, RAND <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19474079>
- 6.** “Ensuring Computer Science Learning in the AI Era: Open Generative AI Policies and Assignment-Driven Written Quizzes”
Chan-Jin Chung, Lawrence Technological University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193437>

7. “Creating a Research Coordination Network (RCN) for Building Resources and Access to NAIRR AI Education Resources”
Sri Yash Tadimalla, Computing Research Association
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193439>
8. “Empowering the AI Research Community through Facilitation, Access, and Collaboration”
Forough Ghahramani, NJ Edge <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193435>
9. “Teaching AI-Ready Computational Science with NAIRR Resources: a “Computer Methods in Science” Course”
Vasily Znamenskiy, Borough of Manhattan Community College of The City University of New York <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193456>
10. “Lowering the Barrier for A Practical Path for AI Research on NAIRR”
Amanda Tan, Internet2 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193443>

Poster Sessions

Wednesday, March 11, 5:00 PM – 6:30 PM — Regency Foyer

1. “Combating AI-Generated Fake Multimedia: From Dataset to Tool”
Shu Hu, Purdue University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193466>
2. “From Nodes to Narratives: Explaining Graph Neural Networks with LLMs and Graph Context”
Peyman Baghersahi, University of Illinois Chicago
3. “Re-SpS: Speculative Sampling with Reinforcement Learning”
Haipeng Chen, William & Mary
4. “Radius: Range-based Gradient Sparsity for Large Foundation Model Pre-training”
Mingkai Zheng, Rutgers University
5. “Video Domain Adaptation of Vision Language Models”
Manish Govind, University of North Carolina at Charlotte
6. “Pier: Efficient Large Language Model pretraining with Relaxed Global Communication”
Shuyuan Fan, Rutgers University
7. “Foundation Models for Time Series Analysis, Decision-Making, and Data Agents”
Yunshi Wen, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute
8. “FairAgent: Democratizing Fairness-Aware Machine Learning with LLM-Powered Agents”
Yucong Dai, Clemson University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193495>
9. “Boosting Generalization and Fairness in Deepfake Detection”
Justin Li, Carmel High School

- 10.** “Scaling Neural Networks Education with NAIRR: Containerized GPU Infrastructure and AI-Assisted Assessment”
Feiya Xiang, North Carolina State University
- 11.** “NAIRR Pilot Expansion: FA2: Capacity and Community for Community Colleges (CC)”
Melanie Williamson, Bluegrass Community and Technical College
- 12.** “Qualitative AI Labeling Support (QUAILS): An LLM-Supported Qualitative Thematic Analysis Procedure for Replicability in Educational Sciences Research”
Jeremy Riel, University of Illinois Chicago <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193550>
- 13.** “Efficient Generative AI for Synthetic Mobility Data Generation”
Guang Wang, Florida State University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193477>
- 14.** “Teaching Scalable Wildlife Image Processing with NAIRR Jetstream2 GPUs to Undergraduates”
Katherine Nunn, Southern Oregon University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193546>
- 15.** “From Evaluation to Actionability: Closing Factuality Gaps in Medical Large Vision–Language Models”
Huaxiu Yao, UNC-Chapel Hill
- 16.** “Measuring Stability Beyond Accuracy in Small Open-Source Medical Large Language Models for Pediatric Endocrinology”
Vanessa D’Amario, Nova Southeastern University
- 17.** “Feasibility Study of Generative AI in Construction Safety”
Xiaoyu Hou, Michigan Technological University; Bo Xiao
- 18.** “From Access to Adoption: Building NAIRR Capacity and Community at Research-Emerging Institutions with Small-to-Medium Computing Programs”
Gabrielle Allen, University of Wyoming; Raya Hegeman-Davis
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193499>
- 19.** “AETHER: Agent Ecosystems for Testing, Hardening, Evaluation and Research of LLM Security and Tool-Based AI Systems”
Monica Ball, Metropolitan State University of Denver
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193458>
- 20.** “The Cell Painting Gallery: an NAIRR Pilot Open Data repository of 700+ TB of light microscopy images of chemically or genetically perturbed cells and quantitative features from the images processed into profiles, or numerical vectors, that describe each sample”
Erin Weisbart, Broad Institute of MIT and Harvard
- 21.** “Mutation2Text: A Unified Protein and Text Language Model for Explaining Mutation Effects”
Oladimeji Macaulay, University of New Mexico <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193530>

- 22.** “Diamond: A Web User Interface for Neural Network”
Haotian Xie, Rutgers University
- 23.** “NAIRR Pilot Expansion: FA2: Capacity and Community for Research Emerging Institutions with Large Computing Programs”
Traian Truta, Northern Kentucky University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193532>
- 24.** “Expanding NAIRR to new Researchers through Sustainable Research Pathways”
Mary Ann Leung, Sustainable Horizons Institute; Kristen Fahy
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193487>
- 25.** “Data Science Applications for Social Impact Through Data Discovery”
George Obaido, University of California Berkeley
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193473>
- 26.** “Hands-on Ethical Inquiry: A Participatory and Exploratory Lab Model for AI/ML Ethics Education”
Changjia Yang, University Of Maryland, Baltimore County
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193449>
- 27.** “Streamlining Assessment: Does Access to Common Compute Resources Simplify Grading in NLP Courses?”
Stephanie Rivera-Moro, East Carolina University
- 28.** “Efficient Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback with Serverless Computing”
Rui Wei, Stevens Institute of Technology; Dr. Hao Wang
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193481>
- 29.** “Conformal Prediction for Risk-Controlled Medical Entity Extraction Across Clinical Domains”
Manil Shrestha, Department of Computer Science, Drexel University
- 30.** “Generalizable and Interpretable Deep Learning for Explainable Microarchitecture Performance Prediction”
Krishbin Paudel, University of South Florida <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193514>
- 32.** “ScholarEval: Research Idea Evaluation Grounded in Literature”
Hanane Nour Moussa, The Ohio State University
- 33.** “Prompt Transferability Across LLMs: An Empirical Study Under Prompt Optimization”
Chak Kwong (Tommy) Cheng, University of Illinois Chicago
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193540>
- 34.** “Computer Methods for Science: Utilizing Advanced Computational Resources for AI in Scientific Research”
Vasily Znamenskiy, Borough of Manhattan Community College of The City University of New York <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193469>

- 35.** “Lessons learned from Hub coordination of six NAIRR Pilot Expansion: FA2: Capacity and Community for 4-Year, Research Emerging Small-Medium, Research Emerging Large, Community Colleges, MSI, and HBCU grants”
Stephanie T. Jones, Computing Research Association
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193526>
- 36.** “NSF LEVEL UP AI: A Complimentary Initiative to NAIRR”
Stephanie T. Jones, Computing Research Association; MAY CHANGE PRESENTER
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193536>
- 37.** “On the Feasibility and Opportunity of Autoregressive 3D Object Detection”
Jinsu Yoo, The Ohio State University
- 38.** “Learning shape morphing of stimulus-actuated composites via Neural ODEs”
Aditya Patil, University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA); Yupeng Zhang
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193522>
- 39.** “Explainable AI with Multi-Agent Collaborative System for Colonoscopic Polyp Detection and Kudo Pit Classification”
Kushal Virupakshappa, University of New Mexico Cancer Center
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193493>
- 40.** “Advancing Research Capacity and NAIRR Access Through AI Ideation Labs at Hispanic-Serving Institutions”
Nayda Santiago, University of Puerto Rico, Mayaguez Campus; Ana Huallparimachi
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193462>
- 41.** “ARMOR-HAL: Unified Defense for Adversarial Robustness and Hallucination Mitigation in Large Vision-Language Models”
Ahmed Imteaj, Florida Atlantic University <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193460>
- 42.** “Empirical Differential Privacy: Beyond Auditing Differentially Private Deep Learning”
Keke Chen, University of Maryland, Baltimore County; Jiaji He & Min-Chun Chen
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193485>

Demos

Thursday, March 12, 5:00 PM – 6:30 PM — Regency Foyer

- 1.** “ViSCOP: Visual Probing for Video Domain Adaptation of Vision Language Models”
Manish Govind, University of North Carolina at Charlotte; Srijan Das (faculty advisor to Manish)
- 2.** “SynthGuard: An Open Platform for Detecting AI-Generated Multimedia with Multimodal LLMs”
Justin Li, Carmel High School

- 3. "Live Demo of AETHER: Interactive LLM Security Testing and Agent Simulation Using BiliCore and NAIRR Cloud Resources"**
Monica Ball, Metropolitan State University of Denver
- 4. "Diamond: A Web User Interface for Neural Network"**
Haotian Xie, Rutgers University
- 5. "BioCLIP 2 Interactive Demos: Species Identification and Embedding-Space Discovery at Tree-of-Life Scale"**
Jianyang Gu, The Ohio State University
- 6. "Hands-on Ethical Inquiry: A Participatory and Exploratory Lab Model for AI/ML Ethics Education"**
Changjia Yang, University Of Maryland, Baltimore County
- 7. "LLMaven: An AI Powered Tool library for Scientific Discovery"**
Don Setiawan, University of Washington SSEC eScience
- 8. "NDIF - Democratizing AI Interpretability Research Through Shared Computational Infrastructure"**
Michael Ripa, National Deep Inference Fabric (NDIF); Jaden Fiotto-Kaufman
- 9. "NAIRR-Enabled Teacher Dashboard for Topic-Level Student Diagnostics, GPT Recommendations, and Personalized Test Generation"**
Daniel Kana Uulu, Borough of Manhattan Community College of The City University of New York; Feliks Altyмышov
- 10. "Computational Student Research Powered by AI in Quantum Chemistry and Molecular Dynamics"**
Bhairav Persaud Tiwari, Borough of Manhattan Community College of The City University of New York
- 11. "eRevise+RF: A Writing Evaluation System for Assessing Student Essay Revisions and Providing Formative Feedback"**
Zhexiong Liu, University of Pittsburgh; Zhexiong Liu
- 12. "Laboratory Exercise Using AI in the "Computer Methods in Science" Course"**
Aaron Sierra, Borough of Manhattan Community College of The City University of New York
- 13. "Interactive Foundations: Perception, Skill Discovery, and 3D World Modeling"**
Shengcao Cao, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
- 14. "Scaling Generative Control for Humanoid Dexterous and Loco-Manipulation"**
Sirui Xu, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
- 15. "ARMOR-HAL: Unified Defense for Adversarial Robustness and Hallucination Mitigation in Large Vision-Language Models"**
Md Zarif Hossain, Florida Atlantic University